

**Diamond Open Access:
Results of the First SeDOA
Ideathon
(November 28, 2025)**

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1. The SeDOA Innovation Lab

The Diamond Open Access Service Center (SeDOA)¹ was founded to support and structurally strengthen the transition to Diamond Open Access publications. The goal is to actively support stakeholders in the academic system and promote community-driven publication models.

The DFG-funded service center is supported by a consortium of 15 institutions², as well as the Working Group on University Presses. SeDOA functions as the German *Diamond Capacity Center*, whose task is to improve the coordination of decentralized services by providing bundled information resources. The *SeDOA Innovation Lab* (SIL) collects, analyzes, and tests innovations in Diamond Open Access publishing. The goal is to further develop publication processes and workflows, thereby making Diamond Open Access more practical and attractive for both researchers and publishers. The institutions participating in the SeDOA Innovation Lab (SIL) – the University of Applied Sciences Potsdam (FHP) – Department of Information Sciences, the Medical Library of Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, the FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure, and the Herzog August Library Wolfenbüttel (HAB) – analyze needs and develop case studies accordingly. The FHP serves as the Work Package Lead (WPL). The SIL team, in close coordination with the overall project, is developing formats to identify the needs of stakeholders in the academic system.

2. Key Results of the First SeDOA Ideathon

On November 28, 2025, the SIL hosted an “Ideathon” organized by Charité. The concept is modeled after the format of a hackathon and provides a space for the joint development and testing of pilot projects while incorporating diverse perspectives.

With the goal of addressing existing challenges in Diamond Open Access publication processes through ideas and potential solutions, the Ideathon brought together 22 participants from the *Open Access community*. Their contributions highlighted diverse perspectives, needs, and experiences. Methodologically, the workshop was structured around several interrelated formats: In Phase I, ideas were generated, organized thematically on a 4-field matrix, and prioritized collectively. In Phase II, four selected problems were fleshed out, followed by a presentation and discussion. Upon completion, the pooled ideas and the results of *the Innovation Canvases* were documented in an open *Codeberg repository*³, where they can be tracked and further developed. The goal of the SIL Ideathon repository is to maintain dialogue with the *community* while creating a foundation for ongoing work as well as for future exchange and event formats.

2.1 Phase I: Idea Clusters

To kick things off, Dr. Alina Kontareva,⁴ an associate researcher at the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society, set the stage for the topic with her keynote address on the question: “What is innovation?” The presentation conveyed a broad understanding of

¹ Thomas Stäcker et al., *SeDOA – Servicestelle Diamond Open Access*, 28 March 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.15043760>.

² Participating consortium partners include the University Library of Freie Universität Berlin, the University Library of the Technical University of Berlin, the Medical Library of Charité - University Medical Center Berlin, the University Library of Bielefeld, the Max Weber Foundation in Bonn, the University Library of Braunschweig, the University and State Library of Darmstadt, the State and University Library of Hamburg, the University Library of Heidelberg, the FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure, the ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics, the Central Medical Library in Cologne, the University of Applied Sciences Potsdam, and the Herzog August Library in Wolfenbüttel.

³ <https://codeberg.org/SeDOA/ideathons>

⁴ <https://www.hiig.de/alina-kontareva/>

innovation. Kontareva emphasized in particular that innovation is not necessarily a technical or commercial product, but can also be understood as a collaborative process in which users, institutional frameworks, and social and political implications play a central role.

During the first phase of the ideathon, numerous ideas for the further development of Diamond Open Access were collected and organized. They can be viewed in the Codeberg file “Idea Bank”⁵. In the subsequent brainstorming phase, numerous ideas for the further development of Diamond Open Access were generated using the Crazy 5 format—five ideas developed in five minutes. This was followed by the prioritization of two selected ideas per participant and their arrangement on a thematic matrix. This process yielded seven clusters of ideas that reflect the key areas of action where participants saw potential for innovation in Diamond Open Access:

2.1.1 Publication Formats: Formats: Enhanced Publishing, Dynamic Formats, Granularity

This cluster gathers ideas specifically aimed at redefining the format of the scientific article. New, small-scale, or supplementary publication types were proposed, such as *nano-publications*, *data reviews*, *reproducibility studies*, *software papers*, or even hypotheses and definitions. In addition, the focus was on multimedia publications (*enhanced publications*), such as the enrichment of publications with images or interactive elements. Several contributions addressed dynamic publication formats; keywords such as “data cycle” or “knowledge stack” were mentioned. Ideas such as 3D publications—for example, 3D-data or 3D-visualizations—or the scaling of publication formats, as well as automated translations into Braille, can also be situated within this context.

Figure 1: Arrangement of topics on a 4-field matrix; Photo © 2025 by Betül Elif Kaynar, CC BY 4.0.

2.1.2 Media-neutral and Accessible Publishing

These ideas aim for media-neutral, interoperable, and accessible publishing and editorial processes. These include plugins for the Open Monograph Press (OMP) publishing software (e.g., for an *Open Source Academic Publishing Suite reader* [OS-APS]), the standardization of technical exchange formats, easy-to-use *single-source publishing* (SSP) workflows, and plugins for submissions from MS Word. A particular emphasis was placed on comprehensive accessibility, for example through an accessibility auditing system, a stronger emphasis on

⁵ https://codeberg.org/SeDOA/ideathons/src/branch/main/events/Ideen_gesammelt.md

accessibility in Diamond Open Access publications, as well as through interoperable workflow management systems and an XML-based workflow.

2.1.3 Shared Infrastructure and a Single Repository Host for Repositories

This cluster addresses the need for shared, scalable infrastructures. Discussions included a *one-repository host* for editorial offices with limited resources, as well as the question of whether SeDOA should provide a central hosting instance for repositories (*shared infrastructure*) for Diamond Open Access processes (e.g., OS-APS, Janeway, ShareLaTeX, Pandoc, Jupyter Books). Further ideas included an end-to-end platform for a seamless workflow from the writing process to publication, a platform for editorial collaboration, or infrastructure partnerships for small editorial teams. Also mentioned were systems such as the *Open Journal Systems* (OJS) for all journals, a global system for journals and monographs, or a centralized service for layout, typesetting, etc.

2.1.4 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

The AI cluster brings together ideas for supporting and automating publication and quality assurance processes. These include AI-supported semantic indexing, AI for XML processes, editorial systems with AI integration (e.g., grammar and spell-checking, keyword tagging), as well as AI-supported template creation for research articles incorporating metadata, including metadata extraction and anonymization. The fact that AI is viewed as both part of the problem and part of the solution became particularly clear in the context of the relationship between AI and peer review: On the one hand, AI was seen as an opportunity to make quality assurance more effective, for example in the form of a tool for plausibility checks. On the other hand, a central data-protection-compliant platform was also proposed for identifying AI-generated texts, image manipulations, and *fake publications*.

2.1.5 Building a Community and Fostering Communication

This cluster brings together ideas for strengthening exchange, networking, and knowledge transfer within the Diamond Open Access environment. Suggestions included editor training, the promotion of collaboration opportunities (e.g., knowledge transfer between universities and universities of applied sciences), and the general development of a community structure for Diamond Open Access infrastructures. Other ideas focused on clear communication free of insider jargon. The suggestion to involve researchers more closely in the decision-making processes of scholarly journals (*scholarly-led*) also points in a similar direction. In addition, concise argumentation guides and a “Diamond Open Access” information package – containing templates for emails, blog posts, presentation slides, and social media – are intended to improve communication and understanding of Diamond Open Access and increase its visibility. The proposal for a “Wheel of Fortune” for scholarly feedback aims to randomly select stakeholders who are not typically reached.

2.1.6 Quality and Reputation Economics

This cluster focused on ideas for reorienting quality assurance and reputation. Discussions included a “*Quality vs. Quantity Control Saving App*,” a cap on the number of publications, and reputation systems that are more resilient to manipulation. Other proposals concerned the recognition of e.g. reviewer activities for Diamond Journals (increasing the *impact factor*), measuring quality through versioning, badges to indicate trustworthiness, and other concepts that promote *fraud-proof publishing*.

2.1.7 Finance

This cluster encompasses ideas for sustainable and transparent funding models. Suggestions included transparent funding provided by academic societies (Fachgesellschaften) or funding associations to support Diamond Open Access journals. There were also repeated calls for

the redistribution of acquisition and licensing budgets, e.g., by reallocating DEAL funds to open infrastructures. Even more concrete were ideas such as a donation button for Diamond OA publications or a tool for calculating the costs of operating a journal. In addition, the establishment of a rescue fund to provide short-term relief for funding and staffing shortages was suggested.

2.1.8 Miscellaneous

In addition to the seven main clusters, other ideas were collected that touch on multiple topics or cannot be clearly categorized. Among others, the following were mentioned: workflow support services (e.g., Sciflow), closer integration of Diamond Open Access and Open Science, concepts for process management, an author contract generator, a Diamond Open Access starter kit, new indexing services, and considerations regarding the governance of Diamond Open Access platforms in the form of a non-profit limited liability company (gGmbH).

2.2 Phase II: Development of Concrete Approaches

Subsequently, four thematic areas were further refined through group work. The University Innovation Canvas⁶, developed at Graz University of Technology, served as a matrix to document problems, objectives, solution approaches, stakeholders, added value, and implementation steps. The session concluded with presentations of the results and a subsequent joint discussion.

This covered the following topics:

2.2.1 Dynamic Publication Formats

The first group addressed the problem that traditional publication formats provide insufficient support for the consolidation, presentation, and archiving of distributed or multimedia data. This fragmentation of research results, data, and software impedes the traceability of scientific findings and hinders their reuse. To address this, the group proposed advancing publication formats, such as dynamic publication forms or modular publications. Key to this approach is an open-source infrastructure with a sustainable operating model, coupled with the integration of services, such as a unified platform for peer-review. The intended added value lies in transparent science, an improved user experience, more effective replication of research, and expanded opportunities for reuse. Implementation should be user-centered, beginning with user surveys, interviews, and needs assessments. In the long term, this should create a sustainable building block for innovative Diamond Open Access publications.

2.2.2 Enhancing Reputation Through Transparent Quality Assurance (Open Review)

Group 2 tackled the rising quality concerns in academic publishing, worsened by the sheer volume of publications in recent years. Enhancing transparency in quality assurance was identified as a vital approach to resolve the crisis. One concrete proposal was the development of an (OJS) plugin for a consistently open review process ("*Total Open Review*"), which would allow review processes to be openly documented. This is intended to both improve the quality of reviews and make the recognition of reviewers' work more visible. During the innovation phase, editorial teams, reviewers, and workshops are to be central elements of co-creation. Implementation is to begin with pilot publications to test acceptance and feasibility. The necessary cultural shift, which goes beyond purely technical approaches, was highlighted as

⁶ Mia Bangerl et al., 'Supporting Sustainable and User-Oriented Educational Technology Innovation with the University Innovation Canvas', *Education Sciences* 14, no. 5 (2024): 528, <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14050528>.

a key learning opportunity, but also as a risk. In fact, the lively discussion revealed that the concept of maximum openness in peer review elicits not only approval but also concern.

Figure 2: Development of the community platform on the University Innovation Canvas; Photo © 2025 by Till Meyer, CC BY 4.0.

2.2.3 Community Platform for the SeDOA/Diamond Open Access Community

Group 3 proposed establishing a German-language platform for the SeDOA community to systematically connect stakeholders from editorial, technical, infrastructure, and service teams. The central question guiding this initiative: “Who can contribute what, and how?” Key innovation tasks identified include *Mix & Match*, bundled and regular training opportunities, and *community calls*. The added value is seen in better orientation, faster exchange, and the targeted mobilization of existing expertise. Success could be measured, among other things, by the proportion of stakeholders reached (minimum 30%, target 50–70%) as well as by short response times within 60 minutes. In the long term, the platform is seen as a lever for Diamond Open Access optimization and quality assurance, as well as for strengthening non-commercial publication structures.

2.2.4 Institutional Levers in the Reform of the Reputation Economy

Group 4 addressed the structural challenge Diamond Open Access publications suffer from low prestige, as existing evaluation systems fail to adequately recognize them. To support the gain in reputation, criteria should therefore be adjusted at the level of funding agencies, universities (for example, in the appointment process), and doctoral regulations, thereby pursuing a top-down approach. The added value lies in increased recognition of Diamond Open Access journals and better career prospects for authors. The innovation phase envisions feedback loops with researchers, while implementation relies heavily on public relations and awareness-raising. Institutional commitments, financial resources, and sustainability were identified as key resources. It was made clear that this idea depends particularly heavily on institutional support, yet simultaneously possesses great systemic transformative potential.

3. Outlook

The outcomes of the inaugural SIL Ideathon have been systematically compiled and are now accessible for review: Both the complete collection of all ideas presented in the workshop and the *Innovation Canvases* developed in the second block were transferred to a Codeberg repository⁷. This ensures transparent accessibility of the results, enabling participants to continue providing feedback and expanding on the documented ideas. The inaugural Ideathon effectively launched a series of future SIL events. In addition to another in-person Ideathon in the fall of 2026, the launch of a new series of online Ideathons is planned. These digital meetings are intended to serve as low-barrier follow-up formats, offering the opportunity to engage in-depth at regular intervals with either an innovative Diamond Open Access idea or a clearly defined aspect of an identified problem. The sessions focus on targeted discussion, joint reflection, and collective design. They are open to all interested stakeholders. The dates of these events can be found on the SeDOA website⁸ and will also be announced via Mastodon⁹.

⁷ Codeberg Repository: <https://codeberg.org/SeDOA/ideathons/src/branch/main/events/2025-11-28.md>

⁸ <https://diamond-open-access.de/>

⁹ SeDOA on Mastodon: <https://openbiblio.social/@sedoa>

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